

Socio-Cultural Challenges to Women's Political Participation in Makran, Balochistan

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Abstract

This research paper explores the socio-cultural challenges to women's political participation in Makran division of Balochistan, Pakistan. The study uses a comprehensive literature review and a sample survey to identify the barriers that hinder women's political participation, including cultural and societal norms. The study uses randomly selected primary data of 310 respondents using semi-structured Questionnaire. The findings of this research elucidated that there are significant social and cultural challenges to women's political participation in Makran region. As a consequence, women have a weak position in the political setup. The findings have significant implications for policymakers, civil society organizations, and advocates working towards promoting gender equality and inclusive political systems that reflect the diversity and interests of all citizens.

Keywords: Political Participation, Social Norms, Cultural Challenges, Maternal role, Wifhood, Male-dominancy and Patriarchy, Makran

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